

Implementation of a Virtual Extensible Local Area Network (VXLAN)

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Abstract – *The concept of Virtual Extensible Local Area Network (VXLAN) in this paper makes a none expert in the networking field have a clear understanding of its purpose, benefit, and implementation. This paper will explain the limitations and challenges the Virtual Local Area Network (VLAN) concept had and how the VXLAN concept overcame those limitations. In this research paper, I will also be implementing the VXLAN technology with some cisco equipment. I will show the command for implementation and verification at every implementation point. VXLAN is a brilliant technology that makes life easier for establishing connectivity within an extensive networking infrastructure.*

Keywords—*networking, vxlan, vlan, lan, vni, nve*

I. INTRODUCTION

A Virtual Extensible Local Area Network (VXLAN) is a technology that takes advantage of network virtualisation's scalability. Virtual Local Area Network (VLANs) were quite limiting in large scale deployments because of the limited number of VLAN IDs. In VLANs, we had a 12 bit VLAN ID which makes us have just 4094 usable VLANs. With the advent of VXLAN, the logical network's number was scaled to 16 million because it had a 24-bit VNID and, most importantly, allowed Layer 2 traffic over a Layer 3 Network.

This intelligent technology has helped check some known Layer 2 issues. Aside from the limited number of VLANs, we still have problems Spanning tree and the increasing size of the MAC address table. Spanning tree helps us to have a loop-free network. Still, we seem to be using expensive equipment inefficiently at the same time. With the advent of server virtualisation, we often have so many virtual machines created with several virtual NICs within a physical PC. These virtual NICs make the switch learn several MAC addresses from a single port connected to one PC. Now let's imagine a data center with several physical machines with a massive number of virtual machines on each physical infrastructure connected to several switches. This concept explains the demand which comes with the benefit of a virtualised network. According to [1], to reaffirm this, the same issue was also raised in its problem statement.

I will further break down this chapter by explaining the terminologies, basic concepts and benefits of VXLAN Technology.

a) Terminologies

Some of the terminologies associated with the VXLAN technology are as follows;

- VTEP – VXLAN Tunnel End Point

In a VXLAN network, the edge devices are the VTEPs, and this is the beginning and ending point of a VXLAN tunnel.

- VNID – Virtual Network ID

This ID came up due to the shortcoming associated with VLANs which has a VLAN ID made up of a 12 bits ethernet frame. It refers to IDs related to VXLAN.

- NVE – Network Virtualization Edge

NVE refers to the portion of the underlay network that sits at the interface and implements Layer 2 and 3 functions.

- VXLAN Gateway

This gateway, just like our traditional gateways, helps push traffic across the network.

- Anycast Gateway

The anycast gateway refers to the default gateway on the virtual network for every virtual machine, and it is set as the anycast gateway IP address.

- Underlay

The underlay network is our physical network responsible for frame or packet delivery.

- Overlay

Our Overlay network is typically our logical network deployed on top of our physical infrastructure to execute technologies like VXLAN.

b) Basic Concept

The fundamental concept of VXLAN is the ability to have an extensive Layer 2 infrastructure which tunnels across an IP Network. This implies that when a layer two frame is sent across an underlay IP network, it will be encapsulated in an IP packet and sent over the layer three networks and then decapsulated at the edge when it's been received by the layer two edge device. Figure 1 and Figure 2 gives us a clearer picture of the concept. [1]

VXLAN is implemented in the data center because it meets the demands of various virtualisation technology trends. A data center scales increasingly, which also has a cumulative effect on tenants. Not forgetting the need for isolation for an increasing number of tenants, VXLAN definitely is a technology that meets this requirement.

Figure 1: VXLAN tunnels between physical switches

Figure 2: VXLAN tunnels between virtual switches on hypervisors

c) Benefits of VXLAN

VXLAN has a good number of benefits which I will further list below;

- Open Source: This technology is open-sourced and flexible among various vendors.
- Flexibility: This benefit makes it very easy for data to move across our network quickly.
- Scalability: The limitations associated with VLAN, which uses a 12 bit VLAN identifier, is being resolved with VXLAN, which uses a 24-bit identifier. With VXLAN, we have 16 million VXLANs as against 4096 VLANs.
- VMotion: One outstanding attribute of this technology is its ability to seamlessly transfer virtual machines across existing data centers with little or no downtime.
- Equal Cost Multipath (ECMP): Spanning tree is a brilliant concept that helps avoid a loop within a network infrastructure but reduces the efficient use of network devices. VXLAN has the ECMP, a protocol that allows the usage of all available network paths.
- Elasticity: With elasticity, additions and reductions to network infrastructure can be made without impacting the existing application process.

For subsequent sessions in this research paper, I will give a critical understanding and context of VXLAN Technology and show the implementation and configuration of VXLAN in some cisco equipment.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Critical Understanding and Context of VXLAN

In this session, I will give a critical look at the structure of a VXLAN Packet structure. As seen in Figure 3 [4], we have

Figure 3: VXLAN packet Structure

the following headers, which make up the frame that the VTEP encapsulates.

- Outer IP Header – This header is 20 bytes in size and contains VXLAN packets forwarded across the transport network between various devices based on the outer IP header. It also has the valid address of VTEPs or VXLAN multicast groups on the transport network.
- UDP header – This is an 8-byte header for VXLAN. Port number 4789 is the default VXLAN destination UDP port.
- Outer MAC Header – this contains the encapsulated Mac address VTEP connected to the source Virtual Machine and the Mac address of the next-hop along with the destination VTEP path.
- VXLAN header – This 8-byte header carries VXLAN information for the frame like:
 - VXLAN ID – this is a 24-bit identifier for the VXLAN. It can also be called the virtual network identifier (VNI).
 - Flags – this contains information regarding the validity of the VXLAN ID. If the bit is one, then it is valid. If it's zero, It means the VXLAN ID is invalid.

We will now contextually look at how VXLAN technology works. As we have discussed earlier this

Figure 3: Communication between Host A and Host B

technology is an overlay technology because of its ability to extend layer two connections across an existing layer three networks by using the tunnelling concept, which involves the encapsulation of layer 2 frames in a VXLAN packet that involves IP addressing. A VTEP is a device that supports the VXLAN technology, and this can either be the end host network switches or routers. From figure 4. As seen in [3] for VXLAN segment 10, communication between Host A and Host B through the VXLAN tunnel between VTEP 1 and VTEP 2. Having a critical look into this figure, we will assume that learning of addresses and the corresponding MAC to VTEP mapping at both ends of the communication is done already.

Host A sends an ARP request to Host B; as usual, a response from Host B with MAC address is gotten, which automatically forms an ethernet frame containing Host B's Mac address and the destination MAC sent out to VTEP 1. When the frame is received by VTEP 1 which already has a mapping table with the corresponding mapping between MAC B and VTEP 2, the VXLAN encapsulation is initiated on the packet by adding a VXLAN outer IP Address header and UDP to it. Within the external IP address header, we have the source IP address, which stands out as the IP address of VTEP 1. We also have the destination IP address, VTEP 2's IP address. At this point, an IP address lookup is done by VTEP 1 for VTEP 2's IP address in order to have the next-hop resolved within the transport network. After that, the next-hop device MAC address is used for subsequent packet encapsulation of ethernet frames meant to be sent to the next-hop device. It is imperative to note that though the transport network are directed towards VTEP 2 based on the information their outer IP header carries, which also contains the destination IP address as VTEP 2's IP address when the packets get to VTEP 2 decapsulation occurs where the external ethernet, UDP, VXLAN and IP headers are taken off and then forwarded across to Host B because it is the original destination before encapsulation took place, as seen in the information contained in the initial Ethernet frame.

2.2 VXLAN Gateway Types

VXLAN Gateway types are a vital aspect of VXLAN, and just like in VLANs, hosts cannot directly communicate with each other across different VLANs, which also remains the same with VXLAN. The introduction of VXLAN Gateways can make this communication possible.

As seen in [4], we have layer two and layer three gateways. L2 VXLAN gateway establishes a connection between a VXLAN network and a terminal, and it also enables intra-subnet communication within the same VXLAN network. In contrast, the L3 VXLAN gateway allows communication across different subnets within a VXLAN and external network. I will further sub-divide Layer 3 VXLAN gateway into two, which are the Centralised and Distributed gateways.

Figure 5: Centralised VXLAN Gateway

Centralised Gateways

We have a single deployment on just one network device for this gateway type. Every traffic across the various subnets within the network is forward through this L3 gateway, where we have implemented centralised traffic management. Figure 5 [4] give a clearer picture of this explanation.

Distributed Gateways

This type of gateway mainly solves the centralised VXLAN gateway set-up problems. If we look at the spine-leaf networking concept and VXLAN, we will find that the VTEPs are the leaf nodes that create the VXLAN tunnel and the L3 VXLAN gateway. We would observe that the Spine node does not know about the VXLAN tunnels. They just push packets in between leaf nodes and not the spine. This technology has just the spine node doing all the IP forwarding at high speed, and the leaf node functions both as an L2 and L3 VXLAN Gateway for intra-subnet and inter-subnet communications. Also, Figure 6 from [4] also gives a clear picture of how this works.

Figure 6: Distributed VXLAN Gateway

III. IMPLEMENTATION OF VXLAN

Our implementation will have a set-up with the use of some cisco equipment. As seen in Figure 7 [5], we have;

- The Nexus 9396s as vPC Virtual Tunnel Endpoints (VTEPs) which runs Version 7.0(3)II(1b)
- The Nexus 3172 runs on Version 6.0(2)U5(1)
- LAN_ENTERPRISE_SERVICES_PKG license installed

Please note that most initial configurations were skipped in this implementation. We have just the configuration of VXLAN to deal with here, and the 9396-A and B are domiciled in the vPC domain, while 3172-A is a physical device. The reachability of all L3 interfaces using the OSPF routing protocol.

The configuration across each device as seen in Figure 7, the network diagram is shown below;

For 3172-A

```
feature ospf
feature pim
feature vn-segment-vlan-based
feature nv overlay

vlan 10
  vn-segment 160010
vlan 20
  vn-segment 160020

interface nve1
  source-interface loopback1
  member vni 160010 mcast-group 231.1.1.1
  member vni 160020 mcast-group 231.1.1.1
  no shutdown

interface Ethernet1/3
  no switchport
  ip address 192.168.1.10/30
  ip router ospf 2 area 0.0.0.0
  ip pim sparse-mode

interface loopback1
  ip address 192.168.2.5/32
  ip router ospf 2 area 0.0.0.0
  ip pim sparse-mode
```

For 9396-A

```
feature ospf
feature pim
feature vn-segment-vlan-based
feature nv overlay

ip pim rp-address 192.168.1.100 group-list 224.0.0.0/4

vlan 1,10,20
vlan 10
  vn-segment 160010
vlan 20
  vn-segment 160020

vpc domain 1
  peer-switch
  peer-keepalive destination 10.122.140.99
  peer-gateway

interface port-channel1
  switchport mode trunk
  spanning-tree port type network
  vpc peer-link

interface port-channel48
  switchport mode trunk
  vpc 48

interface nve1
  mtu 9216
  no shutdown
  source-interface loopback1
  member vni 160010 mcast-group 231.1.1.1
  member vni 160020 mcast-group 231.1.1.1
```


Figure 7: Network Diagram for VXLAN Implementation

```
interface Ethernet1/7
no switchport
ip address 192.168.1.2/30
ip router ospf 1 area 0.0.0.0
ip pim sparse-mode
no shutdown
```

```
interface loopback1
ip address 192.168.2.2/32
ip address 192.168.2.1/32 secondary
ip router ospf 1 area 0.0.0.0
ip pim sparse-mode
```

For 9396 – B

```
feature ospf
feature pim
feature vn-segment-vlan-based
feature nv overlay

ip pim rp-address 192.168.1.100 group-list 224.0.0.0/4
```

```
vlan 1,10,20
vlan 10
vn-segment 160010
vlan 20
vn-segment 160020
```

```
vpc domain 1
peer-switch
peer-keepalive destination 10.122.140.98
peer-gateway
```

```
interface port-channel1
switchport mode trunk
spanning-tree port type network
vpc peer-link
```

```
interface port-channel48
switchport mode trunk
vpc 48
```

```
interface nve1
mtu 9216
no shutdown
source-interface loopback1
member vni 160010 mcast-group 231.1.1.1
member vni 160020 mcast-group 231.1.1.1
```

```
interface Ethernet1/7
no switchport
ip address 192.168.1.6/30
ip router ospf 1 area 0.0.0.0
ip pim sparse-mode
no shutdown
```

```
interface loopback1
ip address 192.168.2.3/32
ip address 192.168.2.1/32 secondary
ip router ospf 1 area 0.0.0.0
ip pim sparse-mode
```

I have listed some show commands that come very handy when troubleshooting to verify our configurations. The commands are stated below;

- Show run Interface
- Show running Interface nve1
- Show nve internal platform interface detail
- Show mac address-table vlan 10

IV.

V. CONCLUSION

In conclusion to the overview of the VXLAN technology, I would say concerning [6] that this technology is gaining tremendous momentum because of its strategic and pervasive nature across cloud networks. And from further studies, we are starting to compare the effectiveness of VXLAN against Generic Network Virtualization Encapsulation (GENEVE), which is giving rise to the question of why we need GENEVE when we already have VXLAN. Having a look at what new limitations exist with VXLAN, the Geneve has been looked into as a new standard tunnel protocol, and also to note that the flexibility of GENEVE incorporates VXLAN, GRE and other tunnel protocols.

The VXLAN technology, as stated earlier, comes in so handy with great benefits over VLAN. This is not limited to being able to place multi-tenant segments across the data center in a flexible way, and it is more scalable because of its extensive VXLAN segment and, most notably, the efficient use of available network resources within the underlying infrastructure.

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